

Designing Experiments for Microreactor Neutronic Validation

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ABSTRACT

The rapid emergence of microreactor concepts has renewed focus on credible validation of neutronic models—spanning transport solvers and nuclear data—against experiments. While an extensive body of guidance exists for nuclear criticality safety validation using critical experiments, reactor-application-focused guidance—particularly for compact, non-LWR designs—is sparse. This paper presents a practical methodology to design validation experiments for microreactors based on neutronic similarity. We define qualitative and quantitative metrics (spectrum shape, energy-averaged lethargy of fission (EALF), sensitivity profiles), and formalize qualitative similarity via correlation, or similarity, coefficients c_k and c_0 . We outline a computational workflow using Serpent for high-fidelity Monte Carlo modeling and energy-dependent sensitivity coefficient generation, and SCALE/TSUNAMI-IP and SCALE/TSAR for covariance-informed uncertainty propagation and similarity analysis. As a case study, we discuss the neutronic similarity between the High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (HTTR) and its critical mockup Very High Temperature Reactor Critical (VHTR-C). Drawing on published benchmark evaluations we illustrate how the proposed methodology informs experiment selection and design.

Keywords: validation, critical experiments, sensitivity/uncertainty, TSUNAMI/TSAR

1. INTRODUCTION

New reactor designs—especially microreactors—require validated neutronic predictions to support design choices and licensing. Microreactors pose unique challenges: compact geometries, often non-LWR spectra (i.e., fast or epithermal), alternative moderators (e.g., graphite, metal hydrides, etc.), and a higher contribution of leakage and structural material reactions to reactivity feedback. Historically, the community has anchored validation to integral experiments (e.g., critical assemblies, mockups, etc.), with strong practice in nuclear criticality safety (NCS) contexts and extensive compilations of critical benchmarks and selection methods for code/data bias and uncertainty assessment [1][2]. These resources emphasize LWR fuel/storage and broadly applicable NCS practice, but reactor physics-specific guidance (e.g., how similar a zero-power experiment must be to a compact, leakage-dominated microreactor core) is limited. Relating to NCS, there is a robust set of work supporting the use of sensitivity/uncertainty (S/U) methods, including use of the correlation/similarity coefficient c_k as one method to determine neutronic similarity, as well as to design experiments that efficiently target application uncertainties[3][4]. Recent work has also suggested the use of S/U methods and c_k for the design of experiments to support validation of tools for novel reactor concepts[5][6].

The similarity metric c_k only addresses similarity on k_{eff} , but it is also prudent to attempt to match the neutron physics for reactivity changes (e.g., temperature defect, rod worth, etc.) in the design of any critical experiment or test reactor. Validation of neutronics codes can be done with critical experiments (i.e., ~zero power reactors), a test reactor, or both. One drawback of critical experiments is that they may not capture the reactivity feedback (e.g., temperature feedback), and/or reactivity control effects (e.g., control rod worth) that are important in an operating reactor. We propose using the additional metric c_0 as an additional measure of similarity for reactivity changes. If the neutron physics of reactivity changes in a critical experiment can be shown to be sufficiently similar, then it may be possible to avoid the costly process of design/licensing/construction/operation of a test reactor.

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This paper addresses present limitations by (i) defining neutronic similarity metrics for experiment selection/design, (ii) detailing a Serpent [7] and SCALE [8] workflow to quantify similarity via c_k and c_0 , and (iii) demonstrating the approach for HTTR [9] and VHTR-C [10], a common prismatic HTGR pair frequently used for validation. Note that other tools may be used for calculation of spectral quantities and sensitivity profiles (e.g. MCNP, TSUNAMI-3D, etc.), however this paper uses Serpent.

2. DEFINING NEUTRONIC SIMILARITY

We define neutronic similarity as the degree to which two systems share (a) neutron interaction environments (e.g., spectrum, materials, etc.) and (b) nuclear-data-induced uncertainty contributors to a response of interest (e.g., k_{eff} or a reactivity difference, $\Delta\rho$).

2.1. Qualitative Metrics

Several qualitative measures can be used to compare systems. It is not possible for all of these to be identical, but overlap should be maximized whenever possible. These include, but aren't limited to,

- Fuel form (e.g. pellet, matrix fuel, TRISO)
- Fuel material
- Fuel dimensions
- Fuel enrichment and burnup
- Moderator type
- Amount of moderation
- Core geometry
- Type and form of absorbing material
- Structural/other materials

2.2. Quantitative Metrics

Quantitatively, neutron spectrum, sensitivity profiles for major nuclide–reaction pairs, and similarity, or correlation coefficients can be used to define similarity. Consistent calculation procedures (same energy grid, same weighting definition) are necessary for meaningful comparison across systems.

2.2.1. Flux spectrum - EALF

The neutron flux spectrum is an important factor in system similarity. A high epithermal flux (as in many graphite-moderated reactors), for example, means that resonance absorption and Doppler broadening will have larger effects than systems with low epithermal flux. A crude but useful measure of similarity is the fraction of fissions occurring in different neutron energy ranges (e.g., 0 - 0.625 eV, 0.625 eV – 0.1 MeV, > 0.1 MeV). Another useful measure of the flux spectrum is the energy of the average neutron lethargy causing fission (EALF).

2.2.2. Sensitivity coefficients – S_k & S_0

Sensitivity coefficients can give the importance of different nuclides, reactions, and neutron energies to k_{eff} (S_k) or to reactivity changes (S_0).

The relative sensitivity of the system eigenvalue, k_{eff} , to nuclide–reaction cross section $x(E)$ is:

$$S_{k,x}(E) = \frac{x(E)}{k} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x(E)} \quad (1)$$

Serpent calculates this value using the iterated fission probability (IFP) method [11].

The sensitivity to a change in reactivity from State 1 to State 2, $\Delta\rho = \rho_2 - \rho_1$, can then be defined as:

$$S_{\rho,x}(E) = \frac{\lambda_2 S_{k2,x}(E) - \lambda_1 S_{k1,x}(E)}{|\Delta\rho|} \quad (2)$$

where $\lambda_x = 1/k_x$. Note that SCALE/TSAR is used to calculate S_0 using the sensitivity vectors for each reactivity state, i.e., $S_{k1/2,x}$. SCALE's TSUNAMI provides complete sensitivities (explicit + implicit self-shielding effects); Serpent can generate adjoint-weighted tallies to comparable ends in continuous energy.

2.2.3. Correlation/similarity coefficients – c_k & c_ρ

Let $S_{k,A}$ and $S_{k,B}$ be flattened multigroup sensitivity vectors for systems A and B; C_{xx} is the nuclear data covariance matrix. The TSUNAMI-IP similarity coefficient for eigenvalue responses is the covariance-weighted correlation of the two responses' nuclear-data uncertainties [3]:

$$c_k = \frac{Cov(A,B)}{Unc(A)Unc(B)} = \frac{S_{k,A} C_{xx} S_{k,B}^T}{\sqrt{S_{k,A} C_{xx} S_{k,A}^T} \sqrt{S_{k,B} C_{xx} S_{k,B}^T}} \quad (3)$$

Values near 1 indicate that the same nuclear-data contributors dominate the uncertainty in k_{eff} for both systems; values near 0 indicate dissimilarity. For reactivity responses (e.g., control-rod worths, temperature coefficients), TSAR computes sensitivities for the difference between perturbed and reference states, and a corresponding c_ρ can be defined analogously.

2.3. Analysis Workflow

To calculate quantitative correlation coefficients c_k and c_ρ between two nuclear reactors, Reactor A and B, a two-step workflow is recommended using Serpent Monte Carlo and SCALE. It is first necessary to establish the reactor states of interest, which are defined by the reactor configurations, or geometry, and temperatures. Additionally, for similarity assessment of changes in reactivity, the "delta cases" should be established. A Serpent model of each reactor should be developed, and subsequent Serpent eigenvalue calculations should be performed to calculate k_{eff} , spectrum and EALF, and energy-dependent sensitivity coefficients (inputs can be found in Serpent documentation). It is important that the multi-group energy structure used in this calculation is consistent between each model.

Upon completion of Serpent runs, sensitivity coefficient data, $S_k(E)$ is output to the "sens0.m" files. This data needs to be post-processed to a SCALE-readable TSUNAMI-B format, referred to as SDF files hereon. It is useful to plot the raw sensitivity data to observe integral and energy-dependent trends for a given reactor. The SDF files from reactor A and B can be directly input to SCALE/TSUNAMI to calculate c_k and cross-section uncertainties. For similarity in reactivity changes (i.e., S_ρ) between reactors, it is necessary to first use SCALE/TSAR to calculate $S_{\rho_{Ax1-x2}}$ using the $S_{k,Ax1}$ and $S_{k,Ax2}$. Upon calculation of S_ρ for reactor A and B, these files can then be input to SCALE/TSUNAMI to calculate $c_{\rho_{AB}}$, for the given change in reactivity. Figure 1 provides a flowchart of the suggested calculational workflow.

Figure 1 Flowchart showing the suggested analysis and data flow

3. OVERVIEW OF HTTR AND VHTR-C

The High-Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (HTTR) is a 30 MWt, prismatic block, graphite moderated, gas-cooled reactor with TRISO fuel [9]. The Very High Temperature Critical Assembly (VHTRC) was designed as a critical experiment to support the HTTR [10]. Serpent models of VHTRC and HTTR were developed for Serpent based on the IRPHEP benchmark definitions. It is noted that the burnable absorber definition was updated in HTTR to address an error in the benchmark that mixed up atom and weight fractions of the B-10 vs B-11. Figure 2 shows the radial cross sections of both HTTR and VHTR-C Serpent models.

Figure 2. Radial Serpent geometry of (a) HTTR and (b) VHTR-C (to scale).

Several configurations were made for HTTR and VHTRC during testing. For the purposes of this, two configurations of each were evaluated so that a reactivity similarity could also be analyzed. *Table I* summarizes the system configurations analyzed for each reactor. For the HTTR, two configurations were selected at different temperatures with fixed rod positions to evaluate the effects of temperature change only and be as similar as possible to the VHTRC case.

Table I. System configurations analyzed.

Reactor	Configuration	Temperatures (K)	Notes
HTTR	30-column critical	300	Rods fixed.
		480	
VHTR-C	HC1 (critical)	281	
	HC2 (critical)	473	
	HP	299-	
	(subcritical pulsed neutron method)	473	

4. DEMONSTRATION OF SIMILARITY OF VHTR-C AND HTTR

Serpent calculations were performed to obtain information on energy spectrum (i.e., EALF and fractional fission contributions) and energy-dependent sensitivity coefficients for both HTTR and VHTR-C. Calculations were performed using 100,000 particles per cycle for 1000 active cycles and 50 skipped cycles, resulting in uncertainties of around 9 pcm.

4.1. Qualitative Comparison

Table II provides a comparison of qualitative parameters of the HTTR and VHTR-C. As most parameters are the same between these two systems, those that are different are indicated by bold text.

Table II. Qualitative neutronic comparison of HTTR and VHTR-C.

Parameter	HTTR	VHTR-C
Fissile Material	^{235}U	^{235}U
Enrichment (wt% ^{235}U)	3.4-9.9	2,4
Fuel Form	TRISO in graphite	TRISO in graphite
Kernel Material	UCO	UCO
Packing Fraction	28.8-30.5	30
Moderating Material	Graphite	Graphite
Reflector Material	Graphite	Graphite
Core Geometry	Cylindrical & Annular cases	Hexagonal
Control Mechanism	Rods	Rods
Absorber Material	B4C+Graphite	Cadmium
Burnable Absorber	B4C+Graphite	None
Power Level (MWt)	30	0
Temperature (C) [Min./Max.]	25.5/463 (benchmark) 395/850 (operation)	25.5/200.3 (electric heating)
EALF (eV)	0.08	0.06
3g Fission Fractions [Therm./Epi./Fast]	0.92/0.069/0.009	0.95/0.043/0.008

4.2. Comparison of Sensitivity Profiles, S_k and S_ρ

Here the results of the proposed analysis are presented. The similarity on system eigenvalue and change in reactivity for HTTR and VHTR-C will be investigated. The change in reactivity for the HTTR will be considered for a change in temperature from 300K to 480K (labeled "HTTR_300_480" in the following figures); and for VHTR-C it will be 299K to 473K (labeled "VHTRC_299_473" in the following figures).

Figure 3 presents the top 7 energy-integrated interactions for each system –these reactions contribute the most to either the system eigenvalue or the change in reactivity of the respective system. These figures help to guide which energy-dependent figures to investigate more closely. Note that for both system eigenvalue and change in reactivity, the top three most important reactions are $^{235}\text{U} \bar{\nu}$, ^{238}U capture, and C elastic scattering – though the orders are slightly different. The energy-dependent sensitivity profile for eigenvalue and change in reactivity is shown in Figure 4 to Figure 6.

Figure 3. Energy-integrated sensitivity coefficients of the top reactions.

 (a) $S_k(E)$ – eigenvalue

 (b) $S_\rho(E)$ – reactivity change

Figure 4. Energy-dependent sensitivity coefficients for $^{235}\text{U } \bar{\nu}_T$

 (a) $S_k(E)$ – eigenvalue

 (b) $S_\rho(E)$ – reactivity change

Figure 5. Energy-dependent sensitivity coefficients for C(elastic scatter).

 (a) $S_k(E)$ – eigenvalue

 (b) $S_\rho(E)$ – reactivity change

Figure 6. Energy-dependent sensitivity coefficients for $^{238}\text{U}(\text{capture})$

Overall, the total sensitivities and sensitivity profiles are very similar between the systems for both k_{eff} and $\Delta\rho$. Several observations can be noted:

- The spectrum of VHTR-C is slightly more thermal, due to less thermal absorption and increased importance of the graphite reflector due to smaller size.
- There is increased importance of graphite scatter in VHTR-C, likely due to the higher leakage.

- Uncertainties in changes in reactivity have much higher uncertainty, and this is especially true for indirect reactions like graphite elastic scatter.
- The sensitivity to increase in temperature is seen in the spectral shift (decreased sensitivity to lower-energy thermal neutrons, increased for higher-energy thermal), and in the Doppler broadening (negative sensitivity to ²³⁸U capture).

4.3. Comparison of Correlation Coefficients, c_k and c_0

Using the sensitivity coefficients calculated with Serpent (S_k , presented in the previous section), similarity coefficients for k_{eff} , c_k , are calculated with SCALE/TSUNAMI-IP for different system configurations. Table III shows the results from this analysis including cross-section uncertainties.

Table III. Integral similarity assessment for HTTR and VHTR-C k_{eff} .

Case	Reactor	Config. ¹	Temp. (K)	k_{eff} ²	XS UC ³ (pcm)	$1\sigma_{XS,UC}$	c_k ⁴	$1\sigma_{c_k}$
1	HTTR	30-column critical	300	1.00380	570	0.4	1.0000	0.0009
2	HTTR	30-column Critical ⁵	480	0.97708	570	0.4	0.9994	0.0021
3	VHTR-C	HC1	281	1.00880	560	0.4	0.9770	0.0010
4	VHTR-C	HC2	473	1.00710	670	0.6	0.9806	0.0010
5	VHTR-C	HP	299	1.00970	660	0.5	0.9782	0.0010
6	VHTR-C	HP	344	1.00340	670	0.6	0.9784	0.0010
7	VHTR-C	HP	374	0.99830	660	0.6	0.9769	0.0010
8	VHTR-C	HP	424	0.98994	660	0.5	0.9759	0.0010
9	VHTR-C	HP	473	0.98259	660	0.6	0.9752	0.0010

¹See References [9][10] for details; ² $1\sigma_{c_k} \leq 10\text{pcm}$; ³calculated as $\Delta k/k \cdot 10^5$; ⁴Compared to Case 1; ⁵Using the same control rod configuration as for the 300 K critical.

The similarity coefficients and uncertainties for reactivity changes, c_0 , are calculated using SCALE/TSUNAMI-IP (S_0 values presented in the previous section) for different configurations in each system. Table IV shows these results.

Table IV. Integral similarity assessment for HTTR and VHTR-C reactivity changes due to temperature.

Reactor	Temperature Change	q^1 (pcm)	XS UC ² (pcm)	c_0 ³	$1\sigma_{c_0}$
HTTR	300K – 480K (Case ⁴ 1 – 2)	-2724	25	1.0000	0.0828
VHTR-C	299K – 473K (Case ⁴ 5 – 9)	-2732	38	0.8586	0.1041

¹ $1\sigma_{q_0} \leq 15\text{pcm}$; ² $1\sigma_{XS,UC} \leq 5\text{pcm}$; ³Compared to HTTR case; ⁴From Table III.

4.4. Discussion

The HTTR–VHTR-C pair illustrates that a zero-power assembly can be designed to share the dominant nuclear-data uncertainty modes with a power reactor, enabling credible transfer of validation. Correlation c_k values >0.95 suggests a very high neutronic similarity [2] between the system, and that they were well-designed. There is little guidance for c_0 in the literature, but an examination of the sensitivity profiles indicates good similarity, but with high uncertainty due to the graphite scattering reaction. Further study is needed to develop guidance for system c_0 target values (which may end up being different from c_k guidance), and ways to reduce uncertainty for sensitivity calculations would also be helpful. This may be informed by data assimilation techniques such as TSURFER (part of the SCALE package).

5. CONCLUSIONS

We presented a replicable methodology to design microreactor validation experiments based on neutronic similarity, combining spectrum metrics (EALF), sensitivity profiles, and the TSUNAMI/TSAR similarity coefficients c_k and c_o . A two-stage workflow enables high-fidelity modeling and rigorous S/U analysis including covariance impacts. The HTTR–VHTRC case underscores that well-designed mockups can transfer validation credibly when they share the nuclear-data uncertainty structure of the application. For microreactors, we recommend early S/U analysis, systematic screening of candidate experiments, S/U-informed mockup design when needed, and consideration of multi-physics states for very small, leakage-dominated cores. Developing a curated microreactor benchmark set—optimized via S/U criteria—would materially improve future validations.

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